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EDITORIAL DESK

Volume 3 of the West African Journal of Educational Administration and Planning (WAJEAP) has a total of ten articles that were the products of well researched papers presented at the international conference held in May 2024 at the Presbyterian University of East Africa in Kikuyu, Nairobi, Kenya. The conference had well over 100 participants that gathered at the ambiance of PUEA environment, which was well attended by over 25 universities across the globe including Nigeria, Serra Leone, Kenya, South Africa, Australia and University of South Alabama in United States of America. All the articles have been peer reviewed and plagiarism checks conducted on them before publication.

I, therefore, want to deeply appreciate the management team of the Presbyterian University of East Africa for making this publication a reality. All the writers and authors are congratulated for passing the stringent measures set by the guild of editors.

Congratulations to everyone, and I wish you a prosperous Christmas celebration in advance.

Prof. M. O. B. Mohammed FNAEAP,

Head, Editorial Team

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HERZBERG TWO FACTOR THEORY AS BASIS FOR MOTIVATION OF TEACHERS IN FREE QUALITY SCHOOL EDUCATION POLICY, IN SIERRA LEONE

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Abstract

This study investigated Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory as a framework for understanding teachers' motivation within the Free Quality School Education (FQSE) policy in Sierra Leone. The purpose of the study is to examine how intrinsic and extrinsic factors influence teachers' motivation and how this affects students' academic performance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, and two research questions guided the study. Results indicate that intrinsic factors, such as recognition and opportunities for career advancement, significantly enhance teacher satisfaction and motivation. Conversely, extrinsic factors like salary, allowances, and working conditions, though important, are insufficient for sustained motivation. The findings show that teachers are generally dissatisfied with the extrinsic rewards offered under the FQSE policy, with a significant portion expressing dissatisfaction with the lack of bonuses, allowances, and timely promotions. Additionally, most teachers reported feeling excluded from managerial participation in their schools, which further reduces motivation. Despite these challenges, teachers who are intrinsically motivated tend to have a more positive influence on student outcomes. The study recommends that the FQSE policy be revised to provide more comprehensive financial incentives, regular promotions, and increased professional development opportunities to improve teacher motivation and, consequently, student performance.

Keywords: Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, Teacher Motivation, Free Quality School Education, Academic Performance, Sierra Leone

Introduction

Motivation is a key factor in determining the performance of employees in any sector, especially in education, where teachers play a pivotal role in shaping the academic success of students. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, also known as the Motivation-Hygiene Theory, provides a useful framework for understanding what motivates employees. Herzberg (1967) distinguishes between *motivators*—intrinsic factors that lead to job satisfaction—and *hygiene factors*—extrinsic elements that prevent job dissatisfaction but do not directly result in long-term motivation. In the context of education, intrinsic motivators such as recognition, achievement, responsibility, and opportunities for career advancement can significantly enhance teachers' commitment and performance. Conversely, hygiene factors, including salary, working conditions, and interpersonal relationships, are necessary to prevent dissatisfaction but do not by themselves foster high motivation.

In Sierra Leone, the introduction of the Free Quality School Education (FQSE) policy in 2018 was aimed at providing free and equitable education to all children, regardless of socioeconomic status. The FQSE policy is designed to increase student enrollment and improve learning outcomes by removing financial barriers to education. However, while access to education has expanded, there are concerns about the quality of teaching and student performance, particularly in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination

(WASSCE). According to the Ministry of Basic and Senior Secondary Education (MBSSE), student performance in WASSCE has remained suboptimal, with low percentages of students obtaining passing grades in key subjects like English and Mathematics (MBSSE, 2022).

One of the factors contributing to these challenges is teacher motivation. Studies show that motivated teachers are more likely to foster positive learning environments, improve student engagement, and enhance academic performance (Wambugu et al., 2018). However, in Sierra Leone, teachers under the FQSE policy face numerous challenges that impact their motivation, including inadequate remuneration, poor working conditions, and limited opportunities for professional development (Vibbi & Mohammed, 2023). These issues highlight the relevance of Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory in examining the factors that affect teacher motivation and job satisfaction within the FQSE framework.

Intrinsic motivators such as recognition for good performance and opportunities for professional growth are crucial in enhancing teacher satisfaction and motivation. For example, teachers who feel valued and appreciated for their contributions are more likely to be committed to their work and to go beyond basic duties in helping students succeed (Trowbridge & Laval, 2021; Oluwalola, 2023). On the other hand, extrinsic factors like poor salaries and inadequate teaching resources can lead to dissatisfaction and disengagement, even if intrinsic motivators are present. As Herzberg (1967) noted, hygiene factors do not motivate employees but are essential to prevent dissatisfaction. In the absence of these basic needs, teachers are unlikely to perform at their best, which in turn affects student outcomes.

The success of the FQSE policy, therefore, depends not only on ensuring access to education but also on addressing the factors that motivate teachers to perform well. Research has shown that without motivated teachers, educational reforms are unlikely to achieve their desired outcomes (Rabo, 2022). This study applies Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory to explore how both intrinsic and extrinsic factors influence teacher motivation in the context of the FQSE policy and how this, in turn, affects student performance. By examining these dynamics, the study aims to provide insights into how teacher motivation can be enhanced to improve the quality of education in Sierra Leone.

Statement of the Problem

Since the introduction of the Free Quality School Education (FQSE) policy in Sierra Leone, there have been significant improvements in student enrollment and access to education. However, challenges persist regarding the quality of education and student performance, particularly in external examinations like the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE). One critical factor that may influence the success of the FQSE policy is teacher motivation. Without adequately motivated teachers, efforts to improve the quality of education may fall short, as teachers are central to the implementation of any educational policy. While Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory provides a useful framework for understanding motivation, little research has been conducted on its application in the context of teacher motivation under the FQSE policy in Sierra Leone. Teachers often face issues related to inadequate salaries, poor working conditions, and limited career advancement opportunities, which can result in low job satisfaction and reduced performance. This study aims to investigate how both intrinsic and extrinsic factors influence teacher motivation within the FQSE framework, and how this, in turn, impacts the overall success of the policy in improving student performance. By addressing this gap, the study seeks to offer insights into how teacher motivation can be enhanced to support the goals of the FQSE policy.

Research Questions

- i. What is the status of free quality school education policy in areas of teaching and learning resources in Western Region of Sierra Leone?
- ii. Are teachers motivated in terms of incentives, job advancement and promotion and participation in management in free quality school education policy in Western Region of Sierra Leone?

LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review explored the Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory as a basis for understanding teachers' motivation within the Free Quality School Education (FQSE) policy in Sierra Leone. The review of scholarly published articles draws upon a range of scholarly works, including academic articles, reports, and policy documents, to provide a comprehensive analysis of the relationship amongst the research variables. This review was carried out under the following headings;

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the Herzberg Two factor Theory (Motivation and Hygiene) by Herzberg in 1967, to provide explanation for Teachers' Motivation in the Free Quality School Education Policy of Sierra Leone.

Herzberg Two Factor Theory

Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene theory, also known as the 'Two-Factor theory was propounded by Herzberg in 1967 (Herzberg, 1967). The core of the theory is how to create motivated and satisfied workers (in this case, FQSE teachers). The theory identified factors (factors) that lead to job satisfaction and factors that lead to job dissatisfaction. These factors are categorized into two different groups - 'hygiene factors' and 'motivation factors'. The motivation factors are; attainment, responsibility, nature of work, recognition and career advancement (Chan & Norlizah, 2017; Bawuro et al., 2020). These are intrinsic factors, related to work content and contribute to long-term motivation and satisfaction which, when they are fulfilled would lead to self-actualization, personal growth and better performance. Whereas the hygiene factors are extrinsic, and related to work context. They include; policy practices, supervision (technical quality), interpersonal relations (with supervisor) physical working conditions, job security, salary and employee benefits (Gemedä & Tynjälä, 2015).

Herzberg (1967) argued that the most crucial difference between the motivators and the hygiene factors is that the motivator factors all involve psychological growth while the hygiene factors involve physical and psychological pain avoidance. In order for the management to create motivated teachers, with great level of commitment and performance in teaching the students for increased academic performance, the hygiene factors should be maintained at a satisfactory 'good' level while the motivational factors should be available and present in order to instil satisfaction and motivation (Tasgin & Tunc, 2018).

Figure 1: Herzberg's Hygiene and Motivation Factors (Source: Herzberg, 1967)

Herzberg's arguments can be specified into three key points: - the conditions which create job satisfaction (motivation) and instill motivation in the workers (FQSE teachers) are separate from those that create job dissatisfaction (hygiene); the FQSE teachers would not automatically be satisfied merely by changing the conditions that cause job dissatisfaction; only the aspects of the content can cause job satisfaction and motivation. The theory explains why salary raise may seem to lead to an increased feeling of satisfaction for poor teachers but not for FQSE teachers who have their basic needs satisfied (Abdulmumini, 2021). When a FQSE teacher is focused on salary and security (hygiene factors), it would lead to increased expectations that could be very costly for the school management. "More crucial than the factor of salary is for school managers to increase the intrinsic motivation and long-term job satisfaction for the teacher. This is done by providing "psychological growth opportunities". Thus, long-term satisfaction can only be found in the motivational factors (Herzberg, 1967).

With disregard of cultural differences, there is a tendency which shows that teachers connect satisfaction with the characteristics of the work task (work content) and dissatisfaction with the conditions of how the work tasks are done or carried out. This supports the argument that the teachers' perception of the nature of work and personal development opportunities is central to their motivation. The theory asserts that intrinsic rewards are more crucial to the motivation of teachers than extrinsic rewards. However, the hygiene factor of salary is debated, as it is suggested that it can increase the intrinsic factors as well. It was argued that there are contexts where rewards, such as salary do not undermine the intrinsic motivation. It is suggested that salary is regarded by the theory as only a material, and disregards its potential strong symbolic value. This is complex since monetary reward is a recognition of a well performed work. Secondly, salary is closely related to social status. Thirdly, salary is often the only concrete evidence for the teacher that he or she has performed well. To interpret monetary reward as something that is only a material is to neglect the fact that money functions as strong symbols (Herzberg, 1967).

Conclusively, the factors of a teacher's life that lead to long-term happiness are the same as those that lead to psychological growth and personal development. The basis for this theory of motivation when related to work motivation is that it is hinged on the assumption that humans have certain set of needs which should be satisfied for them to be motivated and committed. The aim is to reach a level where the teacher is allowed to develop and where opportunities for psychological growth are present and possible to attain and where he or she can reach his or her full potential. Motivation is reached by satisfying sets of various needs

and by satisfying the hygiene factors while optimizing the motivational factors (Herzberg, 1967; Abazie, 2020). When the hygiene factors are maintained at a good level and the motivation factors are present, the FQSE teachers would be motivated, satisfied and productive at their job. This would ultimately lead to better academic performance of the students as presented below:

The theory is highly relevant to the theory in that it supports the influence of teachers' motivation on students' academic performance in free quality school education. According to the theory, two kinds of factors exist, they are - motivational factors also known as intrinsic factors and hygiene or extrinsic factors. Motivational factors include - challenging or meaningful work, recognition (rewards), responsibility, participation in management, achievement and opportunities for advancement (promotion), growth and development opportunities. They have the ability to make FQSE teachers satisfied with their job, increase their performance and that of their students. This implies that motivational factors such as rewards and job advancement can help to boost FQSE teachers' job satisfaction and performance. Hygiene factors are extrinsic factors such as company/administrative policies, interpersonal relations, salary/pay and bonuses/fringe benefits/incentives, status, working conditions and practices, and job security that can help to prevent dissatisfaction when they are present. In this study, teachers' motivational factors include - job advancement and promotion, incentives, and participation in management that ensure FQSE teachers are motivated, and satisfied with their jobs which ultimately makes them perform better and boost the academic performance of their students in FQSE.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design to collect quantitative data from respondents without influencing the predictor variables. The population included 226 school administrators (principals) and 5,416 teachers across public secondary schools in the Western region of Sierra Leone, encompassing Freetown City and the Western Area Rural District. Using the Yamane Taro (Slovin) formula, a sample was drawn from 176 schools (92 in Freetown and 84 in Western Area Rural). The sample included 176 school administrators and 1,039 teachers (359 female and 680 male), selected via simple random sampling. Two questionnaires were developed: the "Free Quality School Education Policy Questionnaire (FQSEPPQ)" for school administrators and the "Teachers' Motivation Questionnaire (TMQ)" for teachers. FQSEPPQ had two sections: demographic data and questions on FQSE status, including enrollment, resources, and finances. TMQ also had two sections: demographic data and questions on teacher motivation in areas like incentives, job advancement, and participation in management. Both questionnaires used a four-point Likert scale. The instruments underwent face and content validity checks by experts in educational management. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding values of 0.812 for FQSEPPQ and 0.883 for TMQ, confirming internal consistency. Data was collected through questionnaires administered to school administrators and teachers. The process was supported by research assistants, ensuring a high response rate. Data collection spanned one month. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) were used to analyze demographic data and answer research questions. Results were presented in tables, figures, and charts.

FINDINGS

Research Question One: What is the status of free quality school education policy in areas of teaching and learning resources and financial allocation in Western Region of Sierra Leone?

Table 1: Status of Teaching and Learning Resources in Free quality school education policy (2018-2023)

S/N	Items (From 2018 to 2023, the number of _____)	SA	A	D	SD	Mean \bar{x}	Std.Dev.	Decision
1	textbooks/ dictionaries for use in free quality school education policy programme increased till they were adequate for all the senior secondary students	16 (9.1%)	57 (32.4%)	90 (51.1%)	13 (7.4%)	2.432	.760	Disagree
2	computers/calculators for use in free quality school education policy programme increased till they were adequate for all the senior secondary students	12 (6.8%)	62 (35.2%)	90 (51.1%)	12 (6.8%)	2.421	.721	Disagree
3	science laboratory equipments for use in free quality school education policy programme improved till they were adequate for all the senior secondary students	29 (16.5%)	50 (28.4%)	82 (46.6%)	15 (8.5%)	2.528	.868	Agree
4	furniture such as tables, chairs, lockers etc. for use in free quality school education policy programme increased till they were adequate for all the senior secondary students	15 (8.5%)	62 (35.2%)	82 (46.6%)	17 (9.7%)	2.426	.782	Disagree
5	visual aids such as charts, maps, posters, white chalkboard, globe, bulletin board, flannel board, graphs, etc. for teaching senior secondary students in free quality school education policy programme increased to an adequate level	13 (7.4%)	51 (29.0%)	86 (48.9%)	26 (14.8%)	2.290	.808	Disagree
6	audio aids such as radio, cassette recorder, public address system, microphone, podcasts etc. for teaching senior secondary students in free quality school education policy programme increased to an adequate level	12 (6.8%)	53 (30.1%)	98 (55.7%)	13 (7.4%)	2.364	.720	Disagree
7	audio-visual aids such as television, video tape recorders, film and overhead projectors, computers etc. for teaching senior secondary students in free quality school education policy programme increased to an adequate level	9 (5.1%)	33 (18.8%)	84 (47.7%)	50 (28.4%)	2.006	.825	Disagree
8	qualified and experienced teachers in free quality school education policy programme increased till they were adequate for all the senior secondary students	8 (4.5%)	58 (33.0%)	87 (49.4%)	23 (13.1%)	2.290	.749	Disagree

Criterion Mean = 2.500; Weighted Mean = 2.345; S.D = .779; Overall Decision = Disagree

Source: Field Work, 2024

KEY: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1; S.D = Standard Deviation; \bar{x} = Mean

*****Threshold:** mean value of 1.000-1.750 = Strongly Disagree (Very Low); 1.751-2.500 = Disagree (Low); 2.501-3.250 = Agree (High); 3.251 - 4.000 = Strongly Agree (Very High)

Table 1 showed the status of teaching and learning resources in free quality school education policy from 2018-2023 in Western Region of Sierra Leone which comprises of Western Urban (Freetown) and Western Rural Area Districts using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The Likert rating scale of Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Agree (3) and Strongly Agree (4) was used with the criterion mean set at 2.500. Eight positive items were used to ascertain the status of teaching and learning resources in free quality school education policy from 2018-2023 as responded to by the school administrators or principals. The findings revealed that major fraction of the school administrators “disagreed” that from 2018 to 2023, the number of qualified and experienced teachers (\bar{x} = 2.290), textbooks/dictionaries (\bar{x} = 2.432), computers/calculators (\bar{x} = 2.421), and furniture such as tables, chairs, lockers (\bar{x} = 2.426), visual aids (\bar{x} = 2.290), audio aids (\bar{x} = 2.364), audio-visual aids (\bar{x} = 2.006) for use both for teaching and learning in free quality school education policy programme increased till they were adequate. However, a major fraction of the school administrators “agreed” that from 2018 to 2023, the number of science laboratory equipments for use in free quality school education policy programme improved till they were adequate for all the senior secondary students (\bar{x} = 2.528). This result may imply priority on science or STEM subjects in the free quality education programme. The weighted mean (\bar{x} = 2.345) and standard deviation (.779) clearly indicates that generally, the school administrators “disagreed” that from 2018 to 2023, the number of teaching and learning resources for use in free quality school education policy programme increased till they were adequate for all the senior secondary students. This showed a low status of teaching and learning resources for use in free quality school education policy programme.

Research Question Two: Are teachers motivated in terms of incentives, job advancement and promotion and participation in management in free quality school education policy in Western Region of Sierra Leone?

Table 2: Teachers’ Motivation in area of Incentives in Free Quality School Education

S/N	Items (Since I started working in free quality school education policy programme,)	SA	A	D	SD	Mean \bar{x}	Std.Dev.	Decision
1	bonuses are given to me in addition to my salary	86 (8.9%)	387 (39.9%)	382 (39.4%)	114 (11.8%)	2.459	.814	Disagree
2	I am rewarded and recognised for my performance at work	88 (9.1%)	426 (44.0%)	330 (34.1%)	125 (12.9%)	2.492	.831	Disagree
3	I receive life, medical and motor insurance	79 (8.2%)	367 (37.9%)	427 (44.1%)	96 (9.9%)	2.443	.780	Disagree
4	allowances such as car, wardrobe, and housing allowances are given to me	16 (1.7%)	183 (18.9%)	620 (64.0%)	150 (15.5%)	2.067	.637	Disagree
5	I am allowed to go on vacation/sick/maternity leave while being paid	44 (4.5%)	236 (24.4%)	525 (54.2%)	164 (16.9%)	2.165	.753	Disagree
6	I am compensated when I undergo in-service training programmes	48 (5.0%)	241 (24.9%)	488 (50.4%)	192 (19.8%)	2.150	.789	Disagree
<p>Criterion Mean = 2.500; Weighted Mean = 2.296; S.D = .767; Overall Decision = Disagree</p>								

Source: Field Work, 2024

KEY: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1; S.D = Standard Deviation; \bar{x} = Mean

*****Threshold:** mean value of 1.000-1.750 = Strongly Disagree (Very Low); 1.751-2.500 = Disagree (Low); 2.501-3.250 = Agree (High); 3.251 - 4.000 = Strongly Agree (Very High)

Table 2 showed whether teachers are motivated in terms of incentives in free quality school education policy in Western Region of Sierra Leone which comprises of Western Urban (Freetown) and Western Rural Area Districts using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The Likert rating scale of Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Agree (3) and Strongly Agree (4) was used with the criterion mean set at 2.500. Six positive items were used to ascertain the teachers’ motivation in area of incentives in free quality school education policy since they began working in the programme from 2018 to 2023. The findings revealed that a major portion of the teachers “disagreed” that since they began working in the free quality school education policy programme, bonuses are given to them in addition to their salary (\bar{x} = 2.459), rewarded and recognised for their performance at work (\bar{x} = 2.492), receive life, medical and motor insurance (\bar{x} = 2.443), car, wardrobe, and housing allowances (\bar{x} = 2.067), allowed to go on vacation/sick/maternity leave while being paid (\bar{x} = 2.165) and compensated when they undergo in-service training programmes (\bar{x} = 2.150). The weighted mean (\bar{x} = 2.296) and standard deviation (.767) clearly indicates that generally, the teachers “disagreed” that since they started working in free quality school education, they receive incentives such as bonuses, compensation to attend in-service trainings, car, housing and clothes allowances, paid time off and insurance benefits at their work. This showed that teachers are lowly motivated in area of incentives in free quality school education.

Table 3: Teachers’ Motivation in area of Job Advancement and Promotion in Free Quality School Education

S/N	Items (Since I started working in free quality school education policy programme,)	SA	A	D	SD	Mean \bar{x}	Std.Dev.	Decision
1	I am promoted as at when due	76 (7.8%)	326 (33.6%)	463 (47.8%)	104 (10.7%)	2.386	.780	Disagree
2	My promotion comes with very high raise in pay	92 (9.5%)	374 (38.6%)	401 (41.4%)	102 (10.5%)	2.471	.806	Disagree
3	My school gives me the opportunities available to develop new skills	103 (10.6%)	405 (41.8%)	365 (37.7%)	96 (9.9%)	2.532	.813	Agree
4	State government regularly carries out teachers’ promotion	60 (6.2%)	246 (25.4%)	477 (49.2%)	186 (19.2%)	2.186	.812	Disagree
5	The promotion system has been fair and just	63 (6.5%)	308 (31.8%)	458 (47.3%)	140 (14.4%)	2.303	.794	Disagree
		Criterion Mean = 2.500; Weighted Mean = 2.376; S.D = .801; Overall Decision = Disagree						

Source: Field Work, 2024

KEY: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1; S.D = Standard Deviation; \bar{x} = Mean

*****Threshold:** mean value of 1.000-1.750 = Strongly Disagree (Very Low); 1.751-2.500 = Disagree (Low); 2.501-3.250 = Agree (High); 3.251 - 4.000 = Strongly Agree (Very High)

Table 4.10 showed whether teachers are motivated in terms of job advancement and promotion in free quality school education policy in Western Region of Sierra Leone which

comprises of Western Urban (Freetown) and Western Rural Area Districts using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The Likert rating scale of Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Agree (3) and Strongly Agree (4) was used with the criterion mean set at 2.500. Five positive items were used to ascertain the teachers' motivation in area of job advancement and promotion in free quality school education policy since they began working in the programme from 2018 to 2023. The findings revealed that a major portion of the teachers "disagreed" that since they began working in the free quality school education policy programme, they are promoted as at when due ($\bar{x} = 2.386$), their promotion comes with a very high raise in pay ($\bar{x} = 2.471$), State government regularly carries out teachers' promotion ($\bar{x} = 2.186$) and the promotion system has been fair and just ($\bar{x} = 2.303$). A major fraction of the teachers however "agreed" that their school gives them the opportunities available to develop new skills ($\bar{x} = 2.532$). The weighted mean ($\bar{x} = 2.376$) and standard deviation (.801) clearly indicates that generally, the teachers "disagreed" that since they started working in free quality school education, they get promoted as at when due, regularly with a very high raise in pay. This also showed that teachers are lowly motivated in area of job advancement and promotion in free quality school education. This result may have had negative implications on students' academic performance. To satisfy teachers in terms of promotion that is regular and comes with a very high raise in pay in a free school education, the government may have to spend a lot of money. When the money is not that available, then the government may be unable to ensure regular promotion of teachers which could negatively affect teachers and students performance.

Table 3 below, showed whether teachers are motivated in terms of participation in management in free quality school education policy in Western Region of Sierra Leone which comprises of Western Urban (Freetown) and Western Rural Area Districts using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The Likert rating scale of Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Agree (3) and Strongly Agree (4) was used with the criterion mean set at 2.500. Five positive items were used to ascertain the teachers' motivation in area of participation in management in free quality school education policy since they began working in the programme from 2018 to 2023. The findings revealed that a major portion of the teachers "disagreed" that since they began working in the free quality school education policy programme, they have been adequately included in the school's governance activities such as budgeting process, supervision duties, drawing up the school calendar of events, duty allocation processes among others ($\bar{x} = 2.228$), allowed to participate in decision-making ($\bar{x} = 2.192$), have been given the chance to participate in designing school curriculum ($\bar{x} = 2.244$), and allowed to participate in board/managerial meetings at my school ($\bar{x} = 2.366$).

Table 4: Teachers' Motivation in area of Participation in Management of Free Quality School Education

S/N	Items (Since I started working in free quality school education policy programme,)	SA	A	D	SD	Mean \bar{x}	Std.Dev.	Decision
1	I have been adequately included in the school's governance activities such as budgeting process, supervision duties, drawing up the school calendar of events, duty allocation processes among others	31 (3.2%)	356 (35.7%)	385 (39.7%)	197 (20.3%)	2.228	.805	Disagree
2	I am allowed to participate in decision-making	52 (5.4%)	268 (27.7%)	463 (47.8%)	186 (19.2%)	2.192	.804	Disagree
3	I am allowed to participate in designing work methods and objectives	128 (13.2%)	446 (46.0%)	339 (35.0%)	56 (5.8%)	2.667	.776	Agree
4	I have been given the chance to participate in designing school curriculum	44 (4.5%)	254 (26.2%)	565 (58.3%)	106 (10.9%)	2.244	.703	Disagree
5	I am allowed to participate in board/managerial meetings at my school	76 (7.8%)	285 (29.4%)	526 (54.3%)	82 (8.5%)	2.366	.748	Disagree
Criterion Mean = 2.500; Weighted Mean = 2.339; S.D = .767; Overall Decision = Disagree								

Source: Field Work, 2024

KEY: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1; S.D = Standard Deviation; \bar{x} = Mean

*****Threshold:** mean value of 1.000-1.750 = Strongly Disagree (Very Low); 1.751-2.500 = Disagree (Low); 2.501-3.250 = Agree (High); 3.251 - 4.000 = Strongly Agree (Very High)

These results imply that most teachers are not included in management which may not give them a sense of belonging to the programme. However, a major fraction of the teachers "agreed" that they are allowed to participate in designing work methods and objectives (\bar{x} = 2.667) which is good. The weighted mean (\bar{x} = 2.339) and standard deviation (.767) clearly indicates that generally, the teachers "disagreed" that since they started working in free quality school education, they are allowed to participate in managerial affairs in their school. This also showed that teachers are lowly motivated in area of participation in management in free quality school education.

DISCUSSION

The finding from research question one of the studies clearly indicated low status of teaching and learning resources (\bar{x} = 2.345) and financial allocation (\bar{x} = 2.295) in free quality school

education, Sierra Leone. This finding almost completely agrees with the study by Karim et al. (2023) on “the impacts of free quality education on households in Makeni City who reported increased students’ enrollment and attendance since the implementation of the free quality school education policy in Sierra Leone. George and Murray (2023) in a study noted that some of the challenges in the implementation of Free Quality Education on teaching and learning in secondary schools in Sierra Leone are inadequate teaching and learning resources due to increase enrollment of students.

The finding from research question two of the study clearly indicated that teachers are lowly motivated in area of incentives ($\bar{x} = 2.296$), job advancement and promotion ($\bar{x} = 2.376$), and participation in management ($\bar{x} = 2.339$) in free quality school education. This finding is in line with Brainard (2021) who in a study on “factors affecting quality teaching and learning outcomes in teacher education in Sierra Leone” revealed low motivation of teachers in free quality school education policy in areas of incentives and promotion. This finding is also corroborating the work of Teacher Quality and Management Study, The World Bank (2021) who in a report on “Teachers and Teaching in Sierra Leone” revealed low motivation and working conditions of teachers in Sierra Leone in areas of incentives, job advancement (development opportunities) and promotion, and involvement in decision-making.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory is a valuable framework for understanding teacher motivation within the Free Quality School Education (FQSE) policy in Sierra Leone. The findings reveal that intrinsic factors, such as recognition and opportunities for career advancement, play a crucial role in motivating teachers. In contrast, extrinsic factors, including salary and working conditions, are necessary but insufficient to sustain long-term motivation. The study highlights that many teachers face challenges related to inadequate extrinsic rewards, which hinder their effectiveness and, in turn, impact student performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The government should try as much as possible to invest more into provision of teaching and learning resources to an adequate level for the students in free quality school education policy against all odds. What is the point of naming it “quality school education” without adequate teaching and learning resources for the student? It would rather just be free school education. There cannot be ‘quality’ without adequate provision of teaching and learning resources;
2. The government should try as much as possible to increase the financial allocations to each secondary school in free quality school education policy programme and also monitor the disbursement and utilizations of the funds allocated to each school so they are not reduced but used for exactly what they are meant for; and
3. Inasmuch as it may not be easy, the government should also try to make provision for motivation of teachers especially in the adequate provision of incentives such as allowances, bonuses, benefits, and welfare packages. For the FQSE policy to achieve its goals, it is essential to enhance teacher motivation by addressing both intrinsic and extrinsic factors.

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